

Lithium-ion Battery Fires in Aviation: Operational Risks, Challenges, and Mitigation Strategies

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Abstract

The increasing number of incidents involving lithium-ion batteries in commercial aviation highlights an operational risk that is technically well-defined and has a significant potential to compromise flight safety. This paper critically reviews the fires triggered by thermal runaway events in such devices, focusing on those occurring aboard commercial aircraft. The mechanisms of thermal runaway, the chemical behavior of the cells, the operational limitations during fire containment, and the available mitigation resources are analyzed. This study also examines industry initiatives, regulatory gaps, and challenges in standardizing procedures. Drawing on case studies and established technical sources, it can be concluded that the current reactive approach to the problem is insufficient, given the recurrence and severity of the events. Therefore, institutional attention, investment in training, and continuous updates to protocols are essential to anticipate threats before they escalate into critical scenarios.

Keywords: lithium-ion batteries; thermal runaway; operational safety; in-flight fires; risk containment; flight crew

1. Introduction

In recent years, technological advancements have driven the development of increasingly efficient portable electronic devices with greater operational capacity, consolidating their use in people's daily lives, particularly in commercial aviation. Lithium-ion batteries have emerged as the main energy solution for powering these devices, and they stand out for their high energy density, fast charging capability, durability, and relative lightness. Nowadays, cell phones, tablets, laptops, power banks, and countless other electronic devices accompany passengers and crew members on all air travel, in addition to integrating commercial cargo transported by aircraft (Goodenough & Park, 2013).

However, the widespread use of these batteries in commercial aircraft poses significant risks to operational safety. The chemical composition imparts them with

efficiency and portability also makes them susceptible to catastrophic failure when subjected to adverse conditions. The main risk arises from a phenomenon known as thermal runaway, characterized by an uncontrolled increase in the internal temperature that triggers intense exothermic chemical reactions, releasing flammable gases and rapidly raising the cell temperature to extremely high levels (Yang et al., 2018).

Thermal runaway can be triggered by various factors, including internal failures, overcharging, physical impacts, and excessive heating conditions, generating fires that are difficult to contain and potentially compromising aircraft integrity. Recent incidents involving fires caused by lithium-ion batteries aboard commercial aircraft reinforce the urgency for adequate preventive and firefighting measures. Studies conducted by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) indicated that the propagation of thermal runaway between adjacent cells may significantly worsen the risk, especially in confined and pressurized environments, such as cargo holds (FAA, 2023).

Although there are strict regulations on the transport of lithium-ion batteries, such as those established by the International Air Transport Association (IATA) and the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), the increasing demand for electronic devices and the growing air cargo containing these components require constant updates to risk management practices and mitigation strategies (IATA, 2024).

Furthermore, specific training for crew members and ground personnel is essential to ensure a rapid and efficient response in emergency situations, given that reaction time is critical in preventing the spread of fire and possible structural damage. Technological solutions for early fire detection and the improvement of onboard firefighting systems have also been extensively studied to reduce the impact of any eventual incident (Sun et al., 2022).

Given this context, this study aims to deepen the understanding of the risks associated with lithium-ion batteries in commercial aviation, addressing their implications for operational safety and the challenges faced by airlines in managing these risks. The mitigation strategies adopted and proposed will be discussed to promote a broad and critical understanding of the topic.

2. Severity of incidents: statistical evidence and growing trends

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of incidents involving lithium-ion batteries in commercial aviation. This growth has been accompanied by the popularization of portable electronic devices used by passengers

and crew members. The statistics provided by international regulatory agencies highlight this worrying trend.

The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) of the United States and the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) have been monitoring and recording a growing number of events related to lithium-ion batteries aboard commercial aircraft.

Figure 1 – Annual evolution of incidents involving lithium-ion batteries in commercial aviation, according to FAA (United States) and EASA (European Union) records, from 2015 to 2024. Sources: Federal Aviation Administration (FAA, 2023); European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA, 2024).

The FAA has recorded a consistent increase in such incidents over the past decade. In 2015, 16 cases were reported; in 2024, this number rose to 80, representing a 400% increase. Similarly, EASA also identified comparable trends. In 2015, 12 incidents were recorded; in 2024, this number rose to 55, indicating an increase of approximately 358% (FAA, 2019; EASA, 2020).

Both the FAA and EASA have reported a significant increase in the number of incidents over the past few years. These figures reflect the increased use of personal electronic devices and highlight regulatory and operational shortcomings in adequately mitigating the associated risks (ICAO, 2023).

The data also indicate that approximately 60% of the incidents recorded by the FAA occurred in the passenger cabin, while the remaining 40% occurred in the cargo compartment. The devices most involved include power banks, laptops, cell phones, electronic cigarettes, and portable power tools. The most frequent causes include manufacturing defects, short circuits, overcharging, and physical damage caused by

improper handling or impact during transportation (Snyder, 2024; FAA, 2019).

This growing trend of incidents involving lithium-ion batteries raises questions about the effectiveness of current prevention and control measures, requiring continuous review of safety policies and operational procedures adopted by airlines and regulatory authorities (ICAO, 2023a; IATA, 2024).

The FAA (2023) emphasizes that all lithium-ion batteries, even those that are technically compliant and have a preserved external appearance, are subject to unexpected thermal runaway. Thermal runaway can occur without any visible prior indication, indicating a sudden threat that is difficult to contain onboard. This finding reinforces the importance of robust preventive strategies and risk anticipation before boarding.

3. Case studies: Lithium-ions battery incidents in aviation

Several incidents involving lithium-ion batteries on aircraft have highlighted the severity of the risks associated with these devices, raising debates about safety management and enhancing operational practices in commercial aviation. The significant increase in the frequency of occurrences related to battery fires and overheating has driven preventive actions and revisions of regulatory standards by aviation authorities (ICAO, 2023). This case study presents three relevant events that illustrate the operational consequences and challenges faced by airlines: the accident involving UPS Flight 6 in 2010, the incident with Wizz Air Flight 167 in 2022, and the recent incident with Air Busan Flight 391 in 2025.

3.1 UPS Flight 6, Dubai, September 2010

On September 3, 2010, UPS Flight 6, which was operated by a Boeing 747-400F, departed from Dubai International Airport, United Arab Emirates, and was bound for Cologne, Germany. Approximately 22 minutes after takeoff, the crew received fire warnings in the forward cargo compartment. Despite efforts to return to the departure airport, the situation quickly worsened due to the intense spread of the fire and the loss of critical aircraft systems.

While attempting to return to Dubai, the crew faced progressive degradation of essential instruments and extreme smoke conditions in the cockpit, significantly impairing the aircraft's controllability. The aircraft impacted the ground approximately 27 nautical miles south of Dubai International Airport, resulting in the total loss of the

aircraft and the death of both pilots.

The investigation conducted by the General Civil Aviation Authority (GCAA) of the United Arab Emirates concluded that the fire originated from pallets containing lithium-ion batteries. The technical report emphasized that the uncontrolled combustion of these batteries led to a rapid rise in temperature and smoke generation, compromising the aircraft's integrity and disabling pilot control. As a result, the GCAA recommended the implementation of stricter regulations for the air transport of lithium-ion batteries, in addition to improvements in fire detection and suppression systems in cargo compartments (GCAA, 2013).

3.2 Wizz Air Flight 167, Bergen, June 2022

On June 11, 2022, Wizz Air Flight 167, operated by an Airbus A320, flew between Gdańsk, Poland, and Bergen, Norway. During the flight, near Flesland Airport, Norway, an incident occurred involving a lithium-ion battery from a passenger's personal electronic device, which entered a state of thermal runaway, resulting in intense smoke emission in the cabin.

The crew immediately adopted the established emergency procedures and used portable fire extinguishers to suppress the flames. The captain decided to perform a precautionary landing at Flesland Airport, where the aircraft landed safely. There were no injuries reported among the passengers and crew.

The subsequent investigation conducted by the Accident Investigation Board of Norway (AIBN) identified that the incident was caused by overheating of the battery due to an internal defect in the electronic device. The report emphasized the need to improve rapid response procedures to fires caused by lithium-ion batteries in the cabin and crew training to handle emergency situations involving these devices (AIBN, 2022).

3.3 Air Busan Flight BX391, Busan, January 2025

On January 28, 2025, Air Busan Flight BX391, operated by an Airbus A321-231 registration number HL7763, was preparing for takeoff at Gimhae International Airport (TAE), South Korea, bound for Hong Kong International Airport (HKG). On board were 170 passengers and six crew members. The originally scheduled departure time was 21:55 (local time), but the departure was rescheduled for 22:33 at the request of air traffic control due to the need for aircraft spacing on the departure route.

At 22:04, the boarding door was closed, and the aircraft remained parked in a

remote position, awaiting authorization for pushback. At 22:14, the aircraft's alarm system issued a smoke warning in the aft lavatory (LAV SMOKE) on the upper panel in the cockpit. Shortly after, one of the flight attendants visually reported to the cockpit the presence of a fire in the overhead luggage compartment above row 30 on the left side of the rear part of the cabin.

The crew responded promptly. The captain immediately ordered the evacuation and initiated emergency checklist procedures, while the first officer established communication with air traffic control. At 22:15, the evacuation command was transmitted ("Evacuate, evacuate"), and the emergency slides were deployed. Seven of the aircraft's eight doors were used for evacuation, the only exception was the front right door (R1), which remained closed. The captain was the last to leave the aircraft after ensuring that all passengers had disembarked.

At 22:17, airport emergency vehicles arrived at the aircraft and confirmed the complete evacuation. Fire suppression efforts began at 22:20 and continued until 23:31. The aircraft was fueled with approximately 16.3 tons of fuel and was fully loaded for the flight. The fire severely destroyed the upper fuselage in the rear part of the cabin, even reaching the lower part of the ceiling and internal insulation areas. The wings and engines, however, were not structurally compromised.

According to the preliminary report released by the Aviation and Railway Accident Investigation Board (ARAIB), under the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure and Transport (MLIT) of South Korea, the initial source of the fire was a power bank transported in the rear overhead compartment, which allegedly suffered an internal short-circuit. * The root cause is still under investigation. The flight data recorder (FDR) and cockpit voice recorder (CVR) were recovered and sent for technical analysis. Airbus, the Bureau d'Enquêtes et d'Analyses (BEA), the National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) of the United States, and the Bundesstelle für Flugunfalluntersuchung (BFU) of Germany are formally accompanying the investigation.

Figure 2. Airbus A321 from Air Busan after the fire occurred on board Flight BX391, on January 28, 2025, at Gimhae International Airport (TAE), South Korea.

Source: Korea JoongAng Daily, January 30, 2025.

***Note:** The Aviation and Railway Accident Investigation Board (ARAIB) published the cited preliminary report on February 26, 2025. At the time of the conclusion of this article, the final investigation report had not yet been published. The information presented is based on the preliminary report and official statements issued by competent authorities.

4. Thermal runaway: mechanisms, chemical reactions, and thermal behavior

Thermal runaway is a critical and potentially catastrophic phenomenon that occurs in lithium-ion batteries when the internal temperature rapidly and uncontrollably increases, triggering a series of exothermic chemical reactions. This process releases large amounts of heat and flammable gases, potentially leading to intense fires and explosions. Understanding the mechanisms leading to thermal runaway is essential for improving the operational safety of devices using this technology, especially in the context of commercial aviation.

4.1 Thermal runaway mechanisms

The thermal runaway process in lithium-ion batteries occurs due to the complex interaction between electrochemical and thermal factors, which mutually reinforce each other in a chain reaction. The main stages of this phenomenon include the following:

4.1.1 Internal temperature rising and heat accumulation

The initial increase in the battery cell temperature can be caused by several factors, such as electrical overcharging, internal short-circuiting, and exposure to external heat sources. Inadequate or excessive charging can raise the cell temperature beyond its safe operational limit, which generally ranges between 40°C and 60°C. Excessive current generates heat through redox reactions in the electrode and internal resistances, such as electrical contacts and the separator itself. This initial temperature rise triggers a series of chemical reactions that further intensify the heating of the cell (Doughty & Roth, 2012).

4.1.2 Electrolyte decomposition and gas release

As the internal temperature exceeds approximately 80°C, the liquid electrolyte, which is predominantly composed of organic carbonates such as ethylene carbonate and diethyl carbonate, begins to decompose, releasing flammable gases such as carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen (H₂), and electrolyte vapor. These flammable gases are highly pressurized and can cause a significant increase in the cell's internal pressure. The accumulation of these gases within the battery casing generates mechanical tension, potentially rupturing the external structure and releasing compounds into the environment (Feng et al., 2020).

4.1.3 Separator rupture and damage consequences

The separator is a porous membrane that prevents direct contact between the cathode and anode, ensuring the electrochemical safety of the cell. With the continuous increase in temperature, the separator, which is generally made of polyolefin materials, begins to soften and collapse at a temperature of around 130°C. The rupture of the separator causes direct contact between the electrodes, resulting in an internal short circuit. This phenomenon generates a sudden increase in the electrical current, further intensifying the heating process and causing the ignition of flammable gases (Wang et al., 2012).

4.1.4 Reactions with cathode material and thermal propagation

The cathode material of lithium-ion batteries, especially lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO₂), is highly reactive under elevated temperatures. When the thermal limit of the cathode is exceeded (above 180°C), it begins to decompose, releasing oxygen. The released oxygen rapidly reacts with the decomposed electrolyte, intensifying the combustion process and making the fire self-sustaining. In addition, other cathode compounds, such as lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO₄) and nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide (NMC), also exhibit thermal degradation, although with different characteristics and critical temperatures (Doughty & Roth, 2012).

4.1.5 Ignition and combustion

The combination of flammable gases, high internal pressure, and the presence of oxygen creates an environment conducive to spontaneous ignition. The spark generated by the short circuit or mechanical friction can ignite the gas mixture, resulting in violent

combustion. The initial combustion frequently triggers secondary explosions because of the continuous presence of oxygen and flammable compounds such as hydrogen and carbon monoxide. Cell temperature during combustion may exceed 1,000°C, worsening the degradation processes and significantly complicating fire suppression efforts (Feng et al., 2020).

4.1.6 Chemical characteristics and associated hazards

The internal structure of lithium-ion batteries comprises an anode, a cathode, a liquid electrolyte, and a porous separator. The main materials used are:

- Anode: Made of graphite or silicon. At elevated temperatures, the anode can react with the electrolyte, releasing heat and gases (Yang et al., 2018).
- Cathode: Usually made of metal oxides, such as LiCoO₂, LiNiMnCoO₂ (NMC), or LiFePO₄. The cathode plays a critical role in the thermal stability of the battery. The thermal decomposition of these compounds' releases oxygen, which feeds combustion (Doughty & Roth, 2012).
- Electrolyte: Organic solvents mixed with lithium salts (such as LiPF₆) in a liquid solution. These compounds are highly volatile and flammable, especially at high temperatures (Feng et al., 2020).
- Separator: A microporous film that keeps the electrodes apart. Thermal degradation of this component can lead to direct contact between the cathode and anode, causing internal short circuits (Wang et al., 2012).

4.2 Safety considerations of the thermal runaway

Thermal runaway poses a severe risk in aeronautical applications, especially in confined and pressurized environments, such as the interior of aircraft. The rapid increase in temperature, combined with the release of flammable gases and oxygen from the cathode during thermal decomposition, intensifies the spread of flames and significantly hinders containment, even with modern fire suppression systems. Studies show that even with an immediate response, the violent nature of the reaction requires highly effective suppression and isolation techniques because the release of oxygen by the cathode accelerates combustion and can nullify the effect of extinguishers (Feng et al., 2020; Doughty & Roth, 2012; Sun et al., 2022).

According to experimental data presented by Walters et al. (2014), in a study

conducted by the FAA Fire Safety Branch, the temperatures observed during lithium-ion battery thermal runaway events may range from approximately 600°C to 1,000°C, depending primarily on the cell's State of Charge (SOC) at the moment of ignition. Additionally, as demonstrated in the FAA technical report TC-16-17 (Ouyang et al., 2016), variables such as cell capacity, physical size, and energy density also play a critical role in the severity of thermal output and gas release during these events. This validated thermal severity range, influenced by multiple engineering parameters, underscores the magnitude of the threat posed by such devices, particularly within the confined spaces of passenger cabins or cargo compartments aboard commercial aircraft.

Additionally, tests conducted by Doughty and Roth (2012) showed that temperatures can exceed 1,000°C in less than one second after ignition, highlighting the need for rapid and efficient protocols to deal with such emergencies.

5. Lithium-ions battery fires response: containment and mitigation strategies

Effective firefighting against lithium-ion battery fires requires an aggressive and coordinated response from the crew. The speed of action is critical to contain the flames and prevent propagation. The effectiveness of the response depends not only on the technical execution of actions but also on adequate training and familiarization with specific equipment for containing and suppressing fires of this nature.

5.1 Fundamental response principles

5.1.1 Fire or flame suppression

The first response to a fire caused by a lithium-ion battery during a thermal runaway process is the immediate suppression of visible flames. This action must be executed swiftly and with precision by trained crew members. This step aims to interrupt the continuous release of thermal energy and prevent the ignition of adjacent materials in the cabin, whose propagation could compromise the operational integrity and safety of the occupants. According to operational guidelines from the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA, 2019; 2023), the rapid elimination of flames is decisive for the initial control of the event and must be accompanied by constant monitoring of the device's thermal evolution.

The primary extinguishing agent recommended for fires involving energized portable electronic devices is Halon 1211, which is widely available in the cabin compartments of commercial aircraft. This chemical agent acts by inhibiting the

combustion chain reaction and suppressing the release of free radicals, making it particularly effective in Class C fires (energized electrical equipment) and Class B fires (flammable liquids), as detailed by RTCA DO-160G (RTCA, 2020). Its application allows localized control without causing collateral damage to the equipment or cabin environment because of the absence of solid residues and controlled volatility.

Despite its efficiency, the use of Halon has been progressively restricted by international environmental agreements, such as the Montreal Protocol, because of its potential for ozone layer degradation. In this context, ICAO (2023) and EASA (2020) have promoted the development and certification of alternative agents with less environmental impact, such as HFC-227ea and Novec 1230. However, these still present significant performance differences compared to Halon, especially in critical operational conditions.

In the absence of Halon or when its application is insufficient to suppress the initial focus, the crew may employ water mist or direct application with liquid containment bottles. Although water is traditionally contraindicated for fires involving energized circuits, the FAA (2023) and the Fire Protection Research Foundation (2020) recognize its effectiveness in the specific context of thermal runaway, provided that its application occurs after device deactivation or in conjunction with thermal containment, as part of a cooling and suppression protocol. When applied correctly, water not only drastically reduces the cell's temperature but also helps interrupt gas release and lateral thermal propagation.

However, flame suppression requires more than selecting an appropriate agent. The positioning of the device, the possibility of immediate access, and the correct use of the equipment are variables that directly influence the action's outcome. Fires occurring in difficult-to-reach compartments, such as overhead bins, under seats, or in fixed structures, require a coordinated response from more than one crew member, additional support for accessing the fire, and adequate personal protection against heat, vapors, and suspended particles. EASA (2020) recommends that the use of extinguishers should always be preceded by a quick visual assessment of the area, considering the presence of secondary combustible materials, cabin ventilation, and the risk of escalation of the thermal event.

Therefore, visible flame suppression represents a critical and immediate execution stage but does not, by itself, ensure complete neutralization of the event. The complexity of the thermal runaway requires that this first action be followed by a

structured process of continuous cooling, physical isolation, and monitoring of residual thermal conditions, as established in technical flight safety protocols. Effective responses depend on integrating technical knowledge, operational readiness and the clarity of procedures adopted by the airline.

5.1.2 Battery cooling

The cell cooling stage after the initial flame suppression is essential for interrupting the thermal re-ignition cycle characteristic of the thermal runaway. The rapid dissipation of heat prevents the internal temperature of the cell from again reaching the decomposition threshold of the electrolyte, a factor directly associated with spontaneous re-ignition. According to the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA, 2023), continuous and aggressive cooling is the only effective method for breaking thermal propagation within modules or devices with multiple connected cells.

The most widely used and recommended agent for this phase is abundant water, which is applied directly over the battery-powered device and is continuously maintained even after visible flame extinction. Water acts as a thermal dissipator, gradually reducing the cell's temperature and preventing the continuous release of flammable gases. Laboratory studies conducted by Wang et al. (2012) and later validated in operational simulations by AIChE (2023) demonstrated that the application of water significantly reduces the probability of re-ignition in lithium-ion batteries subjected to internal short circuits or mechanical impacts.

Despite the traditional contraindication of using water in electrical fires, the particularities of thermal runaway in lithium-ion batteries justify their application in this context. As recorded in the IATA report (2024), the internal structure of the cell remained unstable even after the initial flame suppression, maintaining the unit's temperature and the risk of re-ignition. When coming into direct contact with the battery body, water absorbs residual thermal energy and reduces the rate of flammable gas generation, thereby stabilizing the device until its final containment.

The FAA (2019) recommends that crew members have accessible water bottles ready for use in emergency situations, in addition to additional containers that allow prolonged liquid application. The necessary volume of water may vary depending on the size and configuration of the device involved, with the cooling of larger devices (such as power banks or laptops) possibly requiring continuous application for up to 15 minutes, according to operational tests disclosed by EASA (2020).

It is essential for the cooling process to occur in a controlled manner, carefully avoiding excessive splashing, saturation of nearby electrical components, and contact with passengers. The application should be made directly over the cell's thermal area, preferably at an angle that maximizes thermal absorption and minimizes reflux. The use of personal protective equipment, such as thermal gloves and masks, is recommended for the crew during this stage, according to the safe-handling guidelines issued by ICAO (2023).

The success of cooling is directly linked to response speed, availability of resources on board, and crew members' familiarity with the procedures. Premature interruption of cooling or underestimation of residual temperature may lead to re-ignition and escalation of the event. For this reason, this stage demands the same degree of operation focus and technical readiness as those applied to flame suppression and device isolation.

5.1.3 Device isolation

After the initial active cooling stage with continuous water or other nonflammable liquid application, the device must be carefully isolated to prevent re-ignition, contain solid residues and toxic vapors, and preserve the cabin's integrity. Aviation authorities consider this phase critical because the residual heat and chemical instability of batteries that have undergone thermal runaway can result in new combustion points even after the apparent control of the flames (FAA, 2019; ICAO, 2023).

The most widely recommended method for this stage is to use so-called fire-containment bags (FCBs), which are devices specifically developed to contain fires caused by lithium-ion batteries in portable electronic devices. According to IATA (2024), FCBs are manufactured with materials resistant to flame and internal pressure generated during thermal runaway events, and their proper application can significantly reduce the risk of fire propagation and exposure to toxic gases released. Studies conducted by ICAO (2023a) have demonstrated that the use of FCBs, when integrated into well-defined operational procedures, substantially contributes to risk mitigation on board.

Among the models widely used in the industry are the X-Bag, developed by Lion Labs, which combines multi-layer thermal resistance with ease of handling in confined environments; the AvSax®, adopted by several European airlines and certified

to contain devices in active combustion; the FireShield™ Pouch, manufactured by Enersys, with a structure compatible with the use of internal liquids; and the Hedbox FIREBAG-L, designed for photographic equipment and larger electronic devices. These products meet thermal resistance and structural integrity requirements defined by standards such as RTCA DO-160G (RTCA, 2020) and are cited in operational guidelines compiled by the FAA (2023) and IATA (2024). The most appropriate bag depends on the type of operation, aircraft configuration, and level of training provided for its use. The success of its application, however, is directly related to the crew members' familiarity with the equipment, the clarity of operational procedures, and the correct assessment of the situation at the time of the event.

Despite the growing adoption of FCBs, it is important to recognize that not all airlines operate with this equipment on board, especially in smaller operations on regional flights. In such cases, the adoption of alternative measures, provided for in standardized operational procedures and previously validated by the competent aeronautical authority, is recommended. Among the documented options is the use of metal boxes or heat-resistant containers filled with ice or refrigerant liquids, as recommended by the Fire Protection Research Foundation (2020). Although less efficient than FCBs, this method has been widely used as an emergency measure in real events, according to reports compiled by EASA (2020) and GCAA (2013).

Handling the damaged device must be performed using personal protective equipment, such as thermal gloves and respiratory protection, according to the operational guidelines established in FAA manuals (2023). Once isolated, the device must be stored in a safe location, visible to the crew and away from high-traffic areas, without blocking emergency exits or interfering with access to essential equipment.

Finally, the effectiveness of this stage depends directly on the crew's familiarity with the available equipment, the clarity of the procedures described in the operational manuals, and their ability to apply them under high-pressure conditions. According to ICAO (2023), the combination of adequate equipment and trained technical judgment defines success in containing a thermal runaway event. Whether using an approved FCB or adopting an alternative solution validated by the operator, the crew must be ready to assess risks, make quick decisions, and execute containment safely and efficiently.

5.1.4 Continuous monitoring

Continuous monitoring of the device after flame suppression, cooling, and

physical isolation is essential for managing thermal runaway events. Even if the fire focus is apparently controlled, the thermal and electrochemical instability of the cell may persist for a prolonged period, maintaining a high risk of re-ignition. As highlighted by ICAO (2023a), the electrolyte decomposition process may continue even after the visual containment of the event, making constant monitoring an essential component of the operational response.

During monitoring, the crew must observe residual signs of heating, vapor emission, structural deformations in the battery-powered device casing, or any perceptible change in the thermal behavior of the isolated material. The FAA (2023) recommends that the location where the device is stored, whether in a fire-containment bag, a metal container, or another validated method, should be kept visible and accessible to the flight attendants responsible for monitoring. If the containment compartment shows signs of intense heat, internal condensation, or smoke presence, a new intervention may be necessary, including the reapplication of coolant liquid.

Crew members must be technically prepared to identify signs of residual thermal activity. As observed in tests conducted by EASA (2020), the absence of flame does not mean complete stabilization of the cell's internal system. In simulations performed with medium-sized devices, endothermic reactions and exudation of flammable gases were recorded for up to 30 minutes after initial isolation, reinforcing the need for extended vigilance. This latency period, associated with the slow release of accumulated heat, justifies the device's permanence in an isolated location for the rest of the flight, which is always under observation.

In addition to visual observation, ICAO (2023) and IATA (2024) highlighted the importance of communication among the crew members during this phase. Monitoring must be formalized, with clear responsibility assigned to a designated flight attendant or crew member who will remain attentive to the device's conditions and report any anomaly to the captain. In addition to ensuring traceability of the response, this procedure avoids dispersion of responsibility during the critical stages of the risk mitigation process.

The duration of monitoring should be proportional to the event's severity, the device's thermal configuration, and the remaining flight duration. In short-haul operations, the monitoring should extend until landing and aircraft disembark. In long-haul flights, periodic assessment of thermal stability is recommended, preferably at 15-minute intervals during the first hour after isolation, according to internal guidelines

from operators who have faced this type of event in-flight (Fire Protection Research Foundation, 2020).

Finally, continuous monitoring is not limited to passive vigilance. This represents the technical closure of the thermal runaway response cycle, integrating the elements of suppression, cooling, and isolation into a sustained containment strategy. Maintaining a state of alert, associated with the operational discipline of the crew, ensures the total effectiveness of the response and minimizes residual risks until the safe conclusion of the flight.

6. Challenges for the industry

The growing dependence of passengers and crew on electronic devices has imposed a series of operational, regulatory, and financial challenges on commercial aviation in terms of preventing and managing incidents involving lithium-ion batteries. The unstable chemical nature of these batteries, combined with the difficulty of thermal control in confined and pressurized environments, makes their presence a constant risk to flight safety.

One of the main challenges faced by operators concerns the standardization of onboard containment equipment and procedures. Implementing fire-containment bags (FCBs), temperature sensors, and specialized fire-suppression equipment represents a significant investment, especially for airlines with large fleets or low-cost operational models (IATA, 2024). Furthermore, there are substantial variations between operators and jurisdictions regarding the mandatory nature and classification of the minimum required equipment, which weakens the consistency of the global response to the risk (ICAO, 2023).

Continuous crew training is another critical point. Technical training for action in thermal runaway fires requires operational resources, ground time, and qualified instructors, directly impacting the efficiency of the airline network. According to FAA (2023) observations, poorly trained crew members or those with inconsistent knowledge represent an aggravating factor in incidents due to the difficulty in recognizing the onset of the thermal reaction and the inadequate application of containment procedures. In particular, the frequent updating of training to incorporate new equipment or regulatory changes is identified as one of the main operational bottlenecks.

Additionally, airlines face limitations in screening and inspecting battery-powered devices. Control over the contents of hand luggage, especially on international

flights with multiple connections, is limited. Many low-cost electronic devices — such as uncertified power banks, electronic cigarettes, and loose batteries — are carried on board without proper inspection, often exceeding the permitted power limit or showing visible signs of physical damage (AIChE, 2023; ICAO, 2023).

The document published by FAA (2023), aimed at guiding passengers and air operators, highlighted that a significant part of onboard incidents is related to the improper transport of electronic devices or spare batteries. In addition to technical failures or physical damage to equipment, factors such as inappropriate storage, transport of prohibited items, and unawareness of safety limits contribute to the increased number of cases. The FAA establishes a limit of up to 100 Wh for transporting spare batteries in carry-on luggage and up to 160 Wh with prior airline approval. These guidelines reinforce the importance of clear passenger information policies and airlines' commitment to a solid culture of prevention and regulatory compliance.

There are also important regulatory challenges. The fragmentation of international regulations on battery transport, varying between ICAO, IATA, FAA, EASA, and local authorities, makes the uniform application of policies difficult and creates gray areas regarding liability in the event of operational failure. This is particularly relevant in code-sharing flights where the operator, aircraft, and crew may be subject to different rules.

Finally, the technological advancement of devices challenges the industry's ability to keep pace with such risks. New models with higher energy density, multiple cells, and high charging power are continuously launched on the market, often without sufficient time for adapting operational manuals and current regulations (Sun et al., 2022).

Thus, the challenges faced by the industry go beyond equipment acquisition and training. This systemic, multidimensional, and dynamic problem requires articulation among device manufacturers, regulatory authorities, air operators, and training centers. Overcoming these obstacles requires investment and a strategic approach based on technical evidence, international coordination, and long-term commitment to operational safety.

7. Crew Training

Crew training to respond to events involving lithium-ion batteries is a

fundamental pillar of risk mitigation in aeronautical environments. Given the highly unstable nature of these devices under thermal runaway conditions, the crew's response must be aggressive, technically correct, and adjusted to the operational limitations of the cabin. As highlighted by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA, 2023), inadequate training of flight attendants has been a recurring factor in the ineffective containment of thermal events, as observed in various operational incident reports compiled by the agency over the past decade.

Training should not be limited to identifying the initial signs of thermal runaway or the operation of firefighting equipment. It must include understanding the physicochemical mechanisms of the event, the differences between conventional fires and internal thermal reactions, the proper use of extinguishers and cooling liquids, the isolation of the damaged device, and subsequent monitoring. ICAO (2023b) recommends that the training curriculum includes realistic simulations in confined environments, exposure to real models of electronic devices, and exercises with the containment equipment adopted by the airline.

In addition to theoretical instruction, training effectiveness is directly linked to content frequency, updating, and contextualization. Introducing new containment devices, such as Fire Containment Bags from different manufacturers, requires immediate training adaptation, with a practical emphasis on handling, activation, and risk containment. IATA (2024) warns that crew familiarity with available equipment is decisive for the success of the response, especially in situations where reaction time is limited, and the flight condition imposes access restrictions on the fire.

Another critical aspect is the level of standardization and the requirements of operators. Large airlines with greater training investment capacity often offer more comprehensive and immersive programmes. In contrast, regional or low-cost operators may adopt shorter and less robust versions, especially in more flexible regulatory contexts. This disparity compromises the uniformity of the industry's response and creates operational asymmetries with a direct safety impact (EASA, 2020).

Training should also address the decision-making aspect under pressure. Situations involving fires in electronic devices frequently occur during critical flight phases, such as taxi, climb, or cruise. In these moments, the crew member needs to recognize the event, follow the protocol, communicate clearly, and act safely, even in the presence of passengers in panic and under unfavorable environmental conditions. According to the Fire Protection Research Foundation (2020), the ability to maintain

operational discipline under stress can only be acquired through repetitive practical training adapted to the cabin's reality.

Finally, it should be considered that effective training goes beyond the memorizing steps. It requires the integration of technical doctrine, company operational policies, and safety culture. The crew must trust the procedures, understand their logic, master the available equipment, and be able to make decisions even in atypical scenarios or when resources are partially unavailable. Only in this way will it be possible to ensure a safe, coordinated, and compatible response to the standards required by international commercial aviation.

8. Industry measures and safety initiatives

Over the past decade, the international aviation industry has adopted a series of initiatives to mitigate the operational risks associated with lithium-ion batteries in commercial aircraft. These efforts reflect a progressive movement toward adaptation to the safety requirements imposed by the increasing presence of portable electronic devices in the cabin and cargo environment. Implemented measures include regulatory changes, technological advances, investments in applied research, and the reformulation of operational policies by operators and manufacturers.

In 2016, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) implemented a regulatory measure of great impact by prohibiting the transport of lithium-ion batteries that are not installed in electronic devices as cargo on passenger aircraft. The decision was formalized in the ICAO Addendum to the Technical Instructions for the Safe Transport of Dangerous Goods by Air (ICAO, 2016). The technical analyses pointed to the inability of conventional firefighting systems in cargo compartments to contain thermal runaway events in multiple connected cells. This directive consolidates a new level of restriction on the transport of such materials, directly affecting cargo operators and express transport companies.

From an operational perspective, there has been a growing incorporation of specific technologies for containing devices in thermal runaway, such as Fire Containment Bags (FCBs). These devices have undergone certification processes based on technical standards established by entities such as the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA, 2019) and the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA, 2020), which evaluated the capacity for thermal isolation, flame resistance, and pressurized gas containment. Since then, approved models have begun to be integrated

into the emergency kits of several airlines' passenger cabins, especially in long-haul international operations.

In parallel, aircraft manufacturers and onboard system suppliers have initiated research aimed at developing thermal sensors with specific applications in cargo compartments and passenger cabins. These sensors are intended to detect abnormal temperature elevations associated with battery thermal degradation, enabling early response by the crew.

Some of these solutions were discussed in technical panels promoted by RTCA (RTCA, 2020) and were included in technology evaluation programs conducted in partnership with operators and certification centers.

In the field of applied research, studies have been strengthening, aimed at replacing lithium-ion technologies with cells of lower thermal instability, such as lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO₄) batteries. Although they offer lower energy density, these technologies provide more stable thermal behavior under critical conditions and are considered promising candidates for non-critical applications in personal use devices. Sun et al. (2022) analyzed the performance of these cells under simulated conditions of internal short-circuits and mechanical impact and concluded that the risk of spontaneous deflagration is substantially lower when compared to traditional cobalt or manganese-based batteries.

Regarding human factor management, operators have promoted the reformulation of training programs, incorporating modules dedicated to recognition and response to events with energized lithium-ion batteries. The International Air Transport Association (IATA, 2024), in its technical guidelines, reinforces the need for these trainings to include realistic simulations using containment equipment and practical approaches to the stages of extinguishing, cooling, isolation, and monitoring. Crew familiarity with the available onboard equipment is highlighted as one of the determining factors for the effectiveness of the response in real situations.

In the regulatory field, there have been consistent efforts to harmonize regulations among different aeronautical authorities. FAA (2023) and EASA (2020) have collaborated in formulating common criteria for the safe transport of batteries, including energy capacity limits, technical documentation requirements, and guidelines for screening devices during the boarding stages. These actions aim to mitigate regulatory heterogeneity among operators and strengthen the international standard for best practices.

Complementarily, some airport authorities and ground security companies have reinforced hand luggage inspection protocols, focusing on identifying spare batteries or damaged equipment. These actions aim to prevent the boarding of non-compliant devices, especially on flights with high passenger flow and international connectivity, where the risk of non-standardization is higher.

Although distinct in scope and level of maturity, the industry's initiatives highlight the consolidation of a systemic approach to emerging and technically complex risks. The alignment among operators, manufacturers, regulatory entities, and research centers has enabled the advancement of integrated operational solutions that are anchored in technical evidence and committed to maintaining the highest standards of operational safety.

9. Conclusion

The increasing presence of lithium-ion batteries in commercial aviation, driven by the widespread use of portable electronic devices, has introduced a layer of risk into the operational environment of aircraft. Despite their advantages in terms of energy density, lightness, and durability, these batteries present intrinsic vulnerabilities, particularly under thermal failure conditions, which may result in critical events of difficult containment.

This study demonstrated, based on statistical data, real cases, and technical-operational analysis, that the risks associated with these devices are concrete, recurring, and must be recognized as a relevant threat to flight safety. Incidents such as those involving UPS Flight 6, Wizz Air Flight 167, and Air Busan Flight 391 revealed that, even with a trained and rapid response, the severity of thermal runaway, combined with the physical limitations of the cabin and cargo compartments, may compromise the safe conduct of a flight operation.

In addition to the risks inherent to battery technology, the analysis identified operational and systemic factors that increase the exposure to hazards and complicate mitigation efforts. These factors, which are widely documented in international guidelines, include:

- Devices with manufacturing defects or lack of recognized technical certification.
- Inadequate storage of multiple energized devices.
- Inclusion of damaged batteries with visible signs of physical compromise.

- Use of devices with rated power above the allowed limit or without verified specifications.
- Transportation of devices in overhead bins or under seats with difficult access.
- Batteries in checked baggage, hampering monitoring and immediate response.
- Potential for crushing by reclining seat mechanisms or baggage handling systems.
- Difficulty in identifying devices containing internal lithium batteries.
- Inconsistent or outdated training among different crews and operators.
- Obsolete or non-certified containment equipment, according to current technical standards.
- Operational procedures that are excessively complex or of low practical applicability.
- Regulatory fragmentation between different jurisdictions and aeronautical authorities.

These elements reveal that the risk lies not exclusively in battery technology but in how these devices are transported, stored, handled, inspected, and responded to within the aeronautical environment. Operational safety depends on effective technology integration, training, standardized procedures, regulatory frameworks, and an organizational safety culture.

The data and evidence analyzed throughout this study support the need for permanent technical vigilance with a multidisciplinary approach and continuous regulatory support. The risks posed by lithium-ion batteries are not hypothetical, eventual, or restricted to exceptional scenarios: it is present, technically characterized, and potentially severe. It is incumbent upon the industry, authorities, and aviation professionals to recognize the complexity of this threat and ensure that practices, resources, and applied knowledge evolve at the same pace as the devices that are now part of the daily routine of every flight.

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